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ANTIBIOTIC COMBINATION THERAPY: A STRATEGY TO OVERCOME BACTERIAL RESISTANCE TO AMINOGLYCOSIDE ANTIBIOTIC

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ABSTRACT

The global health challenge of antibiotic resistance calls for the development of innovative medicines. Combination treatment with licensed antibiotics using inhibitors that target intrinsic resistance systems offers a different approach to creating effective therapies. Since the mid-1940s, when the first aminoglycoside antibiotic, streptomycin, was introduced into clinical practice, aminoglycoside antibiotics, or AGAs, have been used extensively to treat clinical bacterial infections. However, the bacterial resistance to aminoglycoside is increasing day by day. The overexpression of the active efflux pump gene, methylation of the 16S ribosomal RNA subunit, and alteration of aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes are the causes of bacterial resistance to AGAs. These modifications result in altered AGA structures and reduced drug concentrations in the bacteria. AGAs are difficult and time-consuming to develop because of their adverse effects and bacterial resistance. The antibacterial activity of the combination was found to be not only better than that of AGAs alone but also reduced the dosage of antibiotics, hence lowering the occurrence of side effects. This is because bacterial resistance may emerge shortly after application in practical practice. The development that is of special relevance is a recent one in which AGAs and other drugs have been combined to create a synergistic antibacterial action that provides a fresh strategy to counteract bacterial resistance to AGAs.

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INTRODUCTION

Streptomycin was the first aminoglycoside antibiotic (AGA) to be used in the middle of the 1940s to treat tuberculosis [1]. Following that, several aminoglycoside antibiotics (AGAs) were discovered, such as neomycin (1949), gentamicin (1963), tobramycin (1967), sisomicin (1970), amikacin (1972), and plazomicin (2006), and it was discovered that all have strong antibacterial properties against certain gram-positive and gram-negative microorganisms [2]. Aminoglycosides are composed of amino sugars and aminocyclic alcohol. The main component, 2-deoxystreptamine (2-DOS), is linked to glycosidic linkages that connect 2-3 sugar units. AGAs are classified into two groups based on structural variations: those having a 2-deoxystreptamine (2-DOS) core site and those without 2-DOS core site (such as streptomycin). The core site is further separated into 4,6- and 4,5-disubstituted 2-DOS based on the substituent linkage location. The following is the chemical structure of 2-deoxystreptamine (2-DOS) (**Figure 1**).

The substitution of the hydroxyl groups at positions C-4 and C-5 of the 2-DOS ring and their glycosidic bonding to the sugar ring characterize the structural feature of 4,5-disubstituted 2-DOS AGAs; The hydroxyl groups at positions C-4 and C-6 of the 2-DOS ring are replaced in 4,6-disubstituted 2-DOS AGAs, and a glycosidic link connects them to the sugar ring. The benefits of these sugar units include strong water solubility, good functionality, and a broad antibacterial spectrum because they typically include numerous hydroxyl and amino groups [3]. However, due to the extensive usage of these antibiotics, bacterial resistance has increased and adverse effects such as nephrotoxicity, ototoxicity, and neuromuscular blockade have been discovered. As a result, third-generation AGAs including netilmicin (1976), amikacin (1972), and arbekacin (1973) were created [4]. Based on chemical composition, antibacterial spectrum, and resistance to bacterial modifying enzymes, AGA development can be split into three stages, or three generations [5]. Kanamycin, a member of the first generation of AGAs, exhibits negligible antibacterial efficacy against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) and the binding of completely hydroxylated amino sugars and cyclic alcohols. Gentamicin, which exhibits antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa* and contains deoxyamino sugars in its structure, is a representative of the second generation. Amikacin, a semisynthetic derivative of amino cyclic alcohol with a nitrogen substitution at the position, is a representative of the third generation.

The third generation of aminoglycoside has the potential for clinical application due to its characteristics of low drug resistance potential and high plasma concentration [6], which, following alteration of their mother nucleus, are characterized by the maintenance of their antibacterial effectiveness while decreasing their adverse effects. Subsequent research revealed that these AGAs' antibacterial activity against bacteria that produce aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes (AMEs) was restricted.

FIGURE 1 / Chemical structure of 2- deoxystreptamine (2-DOS).

The market shares of antibiotics with fewer side effects, like fluoroquinolones and β -lactam antibiotics, have led to the development and use of broad-spectrum antibiotics. Consequently, the hunt for novel AGAs has been slowed down. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL), carbapenemase of microorganisms[7], and AME-producing bacteria are among the multidrug-resistant Enterobacteriaceae that are targeted by plazomicin (formerly ACHN-490), a new type of parenteral medication that was approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in June 2018 for the treatment of complicated urinary tract infections (cUTI) and pyelonephritis brought on by microorganisms[8].

The United States' first threat report on antibiotic-resistant (AR) bacteria was published in 2013 by the Centers for Disease Control (CDC). The US Antibiotic Resistance Concern 2019 (AR Threat Report 2019) from the CDC highlights the continued concern of antibiotic resistance in the US by providing the most recent estimates of the number of bacterial illnesses and fatalities across the country. Every year, about 2.8 million infections due to antibiotic resistance happen in the US, and over 35,000 individuals pass away from infections. Despite the growing threat of antibiotic resistance in the United States, as evidenced by the rise in drug-resistant invasive group A streptococcus (351%), drug-resistant *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* (124%), and ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae (50%), new data from the CDC shows that fewer people have died since the 2013 report, with a decrease of 18% in total deaths and a decrease of 28% in-hospital deaths related to antibiotic resistance (Antibiotic resistance threats in the United States, 2019,2019).

TABLE 1: Resistant rate of common gram-positive cocci to gentamicin.

Genus names	Bacteria names	Resistance rate (%)
<i>Staphylococcus spp.</i>	1. <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	20.7
	2. Methicillin resistant bacteria of <i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	20.9
	3. Other staphylococcus bacteria (except <i>pseudointermediate staphylococcus & Staphylococcus schleiferi</i>)	25.4
	4. Methicillin-sensitive strain of <i>S. aureus</i>	8.5
	5. Methicillin-sensitive strain of <i>S. epidermidis</i>	5.2
	6. Other staphylococcus bacteria (except <i>pseudointermediate staphylococcus & Staphylococcus schleiferi</i>)	1.3
<i>Enterococcus spp.</i>	1. <i>E. faecalis</i>	36.6
	2. <i>E. faecium</i>	45.0

The Chinese Journal of Infection and Chemotherapy released the results of the 2020 CHINET surveillance of bacterial resistance in July 2021 [9]. Clinical isolates from 52 hospitals located in various regions of China were examined for drug susceptibility to antibacterial medicines. The 2020 Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) Drug Sensitivity Judgment Standard was used as the basis for the judgment criteria. The percentages of clinical isolates of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria that were obtained from the 52 hospitals mentioned above in 2020 were 28.1% and 71.9, respectively. When gentamicin, a typical AGA medication, was tested on gram-positive cocci, it was discovered that enterococcus (*E. faecium*), enterococcus faecalis (*E. faecalis*), and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) had severe gentamicin resistance. Gentamicin was effective against the majority of methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococci* (Table 1).

Following the statistical analysis of bacterial resistance rates to gentamicin and amikacin in enterobacterial strains of gram-negative bacilli with a high rate of clinical isolation, it was discovered that *Klebsiella* was resistant to both antibiotics. *Gentamicin* and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) are considerable whereas *E. Coli* is comparatively amikacin-sensitive, and severe. Among gram-negative bacilli that do not ferment, *P. aeruginosa* was mostly sensitive to gentamicin and amikacin, while *Acinetobacter* was extremely resistant to both AGAs (Table 2) [9].

TABLE 2: Resistant rate of common gram-negative bacilli to gentamicin and amikacin.

Genus names	Bacteria names	Resistant rate of gentamicin (%)	Resistant rate of amikacin (%)
<i>Enterobacterale spp.</i>	1. <i>Escherichia coli</i>	37.4	2.7
	2. <i>Klebsiella</i>	28.9	15.7
Non-fermentative gram-negative bacilli	1. <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	8.3	4.5
	2. <i>Acinetobacter</i>	65.3	50.7

ANTIBACTERIAL MECHANISM OF AMINOGLYCOSIDE ANTIBIOTICS:

Since they are all bactericidal antibiotics, AGAs share a common mode of action that may be broken down into two primary stages:

- Transport of the aminoglycoside through the bacterial cell wall and cytoplasmic membrane.
- Inhibition of protein synthesis by binding to ribosomes.

Aminoglycoside transport into the bacterial cell involves several steps. They spread throughout the gram-negative bacteria's outer coat via porous channels. Crossing the cytoplasmic membrane to enter from the periplasmic area that is carrier-mediated which is linked to the electron transport chain. Consequently, penetration depends on when a polarized membrane is maintained and on aerobic activities that require oxygen (energy-dependent phase I or EDP1 entry).

Under anaerobic conditions, these activities are inactivated; facultative anaerobes are more robust and anaerobes are not sensitive when the oxygen supply is inadequate. Infiltration Additionally benefits from a high pH; aminoglycosides are 20 times more active in an alkaline environment than in an acidic medium. anti-bacterial cell wall inhibitors Vancomycin and β -lactams facilitate the entrance of aminoglycosides and exhibit synergism.

FIGURE 2: Antimicrobial mechanisms of aminoglycoside antibiotics.

Streptomycin binds to 30S ribosomes once it has entered the bacterial cell, while other aminoglycosides bind to different locations on the 50S subunit as well as the 30S-50S interface. Studies have revealed that tRNA and the 30S subunit bind to three different sites: the aminoacyl (A), peptide (P), and exit (E) sites (Tsai et al., 2013). AGAs' strong bactericidal action is primarily caused by their particular binding to the A site of the bacterial ribosomal 30S subunit 16S rRNA. This binding interferes with the intracellular translation process of the bacteria, preventing them from synthesizing proteins (Fig. 3).

Inhibit the creation of polysomes, and encourage their disaggregation into monosomes, resulting in the attachment of only one ribosome to each mRNA strand. When an aminoglycoside binds to the 30S-50S junction, the mRNA codon recognition is distorted, which leads to incorrect code interpretation. One or more incorrect amino acids are inserted into the peptide chain and/or Peptides of irregular lengths are generated. Various aminoglycosides lead to misreading to varying degrees based on having a particular affinity for certain ribosomal proteins.

However, in contrast to other commonly used inhibitors of protein synthesis, such as tetracycline, macrolides, clindamycin, and chloramphenicol, which are bacteriostatic antibiotics, AGAs are bactericidal antibiotics [10]. Current research findings indicate that aminoglycoside is bactericidal when gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria are exposed to antibiotics and promote hydroxyl free radicals that are detrimental to the bacteria, eventually causing the bacteria to die, but medications that are bacteriostatic do not encourage the generation of hydroxyl free radicals [11].

ADVERSE EFFECT OF AMINOGLYCOSIDE ANTIBIOTICS:

All members experience the harmful effects of the aminoglycosides; however, the relative propensity varies (Table 3). The following are aminoglycoside's primary side effects:

1. Ototoxicity:

This is the most significant side effect connected to treatment that is related to dosage and duration. A specific aminoglycoside may mainly impact the vestibular or cochlear portions. When the plasma concentration drops, these medications, which are concentrated in the labyrinthine fluid, are gradually extracted from it. Ototoxicity increases when a drug's plasma concentration is consistently high and over a threshold. This is thought to be approximately 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for gentamicin; if the trough level is higher, the vestibular injury becomes concentration-dependent. To prevent toxicity, it is advised that the dosage of Gentamicin be adjusted so that the detected trough plasma concentration is less than 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The vestibular/cochlear sensory cells and hairs experience destructive alterations that are contingent on attention. Aminoglycoside are not recommended in patients with perforated eardrums because they can cause ototoxicity.

2. Nephrotoxicity:

It shows up as a tubular injury that causes albuminuria, low g.f.r., nitrogen retention, loss of urine concentrating ability, and casts. Aminoglycosides accumulate in the renal cortex (proximal tubules) to a high concentration, and the patient's overall dosage is correlated with toxicity. However, a single daily dose strategy seems to result in less nephrotoxicity in people with normal renal function than the conventional thrice daily dosing approach. The elderly and those with a history of kidney illness are more likely to experience it. Renal impairment brought on by aminoglycosides is completely reversible as long as the medication is stopped as soon as possible. There is a theory that suggests aminoglycosides cause disruptions to the kidney's PG synthesis, which in turn causes the decreased g.f.r. Reduced antibiotic clearance leading to greater and more lasting blood levels and increased ototoxicity is a significant consequence of aminoglycoside-induced nephrotoxicity. Compared to other aminoglycosides, streptomycin, and potentially tobramycin have a lower nephrotoxic effect.

3. Neuromuscular blockade:

Every aminoglycoside lowers the motor nerve terminals' production of ACh. They reduce the sensitivity of the muscle endplates to ACh and obstruct the mobilization of centrally positioned synaptic vesicles to fuse with the terminal membrane (perhaps by inhibiting Ca²⁺). In the therapeutic application of these medications, the effect of this action does not usually show up. However, when streptomycin or neomycin was injected into the peritoneal or pleural cavity following surgery, apnoea and deaths happened, particularly if a curare-like muscle relaxant was used during the procedure. Quick absorption from the peritoneum or pleura results in elevated blood levels and intensifies the neuromuscular blocker's persistent effects.

TABLE 3 / Comparative toxicity of aminoglycoside antibiotics.

Systemically used aminoglycoside	Ototoxicity		Nephrotoxicity
	Vestibular	Cochlear	
➤ Streptomycin	++	±	+
➤ Gentamicin	++	+	++
➤ Kanamycin	+	++	++
➤ Tobramycin	+±	+	+
➤ Amikacin	+	++	++
➤ Sisomicin	++	+	++
➤ Netilmicin	++	+	++

BACTERIAL RESISTANCE MECHANISM TO AMINOGLYCOSIDE ANTIBIOTICS:

1. Enzymatic Modification of Aminoglycoside Antibiotics:

AMEs are the most prevalent type of bacterial resistance mechanism to AGAs among others [12]. AMEs are classified into three categories of aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes: phosphotransferases (APHs), acetyltransferases (AACs), and adenylation transferases (ANTs). These AMEs alter the NH₃ or OH groups of AGAs to render them inactive by using cofactors, acetyl-coenzyme A, or ATP. Aminoglycoside resistance spreads from bacterium to bacterium through the transfer of AME-encoding genes, which are typically carried on plasmids [13]. The AME gene is reported to be encoded on the same plasmid as the 16S ribosomal RNA methyltransferases (RMTase) gene. Multiple AME genes are frequently found in clinically isolated aminoglycoside-resistant bacteria. There are numerous subtypes among the three categories of AMEs, each having a distinct resistance to AGAs.

1.1 Acetyltransferases:

Acetyltransferases (AACs) belong to the N-acetyltransferase (GNAT) superfamily and acetylate the amino group (-NH₂) on aminoglycoside molecules. AACs may be connected to general control non-depressible 5 (GCN5). Four subtypes of the enzyme—AAC (1), (2'), (3), and (6')—are distinguished based on where catalytic acetylation occurs [14].

The genes encoding AAC (6') enzymes have been discovered in plasmids, chromosomes, and mobile genetic elements. These enzymes are widely distributed and by far the most prevalent in both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria [15]. ESKAPE (E. faecium, staphylococcus aureus (S. aureus), klebsiella pneumoniae (K. pneumoniae), acinetobacter baumannii, P. aeruginosa, and enterobacter) is a group of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria that are highly resistant to antibiotics, including AGAs. AAC (6') -Ib is the most prevalent gram-negative component of the AME genes they possess. N-acetyltransferase AAC (3)-I was created as a specific marker for oomycete transformation mediated by gentamicin. It was discovered that N-acetyltransferase AAC (3)-I was responsible for gentamicin resistance in phytophthora infestans and phytophthora palmivora.

1.2 Phosphotransferases:

Phosphotransferase (APH) enzymes are classified into seven subtypes: APH (2'), (3'), (3''), (4), (6), (7'), and (9). These enzymes transfer a phosphate group from ATP to the hydroxyl group (-OH) on the aminoglycoside molecule. The multicopy plasmid RSF1010, covering 8,684 bp, is capable of replicating in the majority of gram-positive and gram-negative actinomycetes and was found to host the aph (6) -Id gene initially. This plasmid is also the first source of another APH- aph (3'') -Ib, which is located next to aph (6) -Id. The aph (6) -Id and aph (3'') -Ib genes were discovered in both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria as a result of the dissemination of this DNA fragment. Amikacin, kanamycin, and neomycin resistance in AGAs is induced by APH (3') enzymes.

1.3 Adenyl Transferases:

The adenosine monophosphate (AMP) group of ATP is transferred to the hydroxyl group (-OH) of aminoglycoside molecules by adenyl transferase (ANT) enzymes. This enzyme is classified into five classes: ANT (2'), (3'), (4'), (6), and (9). A common gene cassette found in class 1 and class 2 integrons, ANT (2'')-Ia is an enzyme that is typically encoded by plasmids and transposons [16]. This enzyme causes resistance to non-fermentative gram-negative bacteria and gentamicin, tobramycin, dibecacin, sisomicin, and kanamycin those belonging to Enterobacteriaceae. Although ANTs are less common in Enterobacteriaceae and *P. aeruginosa* than AACs and APHs, they nevertheless play a significant role in bacterial resistance to AGAs.

2. Decreased Drug Accumulation

2.1 Increased Efflux Pumps:

Several methods of antibiotic resistance depend on the active efflux of drugs from bacteria. Antibiotic resistance levels can be markedly increased by its interaction with other drug resistance mechanisms, including alterations in membrane permeability, enzymatic modification of antibiotics, and modifications to the target of antibiotic activity. Low-level intrinsic resistance to AGAs is provided by the MexXY-OprM system in *P. aeruginosa*, and mutations in the mexZ repressor, which are produced from the mexXY operon, provide broad resistance to AGAs in clinical isolates [17]. The AcrAD-TolC system causes the efflux of AGAs and other antibiotics in *E. coli* and other Enterobacteriaceae spp.

It is rare to describe the clinical resistance of Enterobacteriaceae spp. to AGAs through active efflux pumps, possibly due to the importance of AMEs in the mechanism of AGAs resistance.

2.2 Biofilm Formation:

Bacterial biofilm formation increases the bacteria's ability to infect the host, and this is typically linked to invasive germs causing persistent illnesses [18]. A biofilm is a group of microorganisms that are immersed in an extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) matrix and adhered to the surface of either living or non-living objects. EPSs include proteins, extracellular polysaccharides, and extracellular DNA (eDNA). Cell lysis produces eDNA, which is a crucial component of the biofilm. *P. aeruginosa*'s eDNA has the ability to acidify the environment and activate the PhoPQ and PMrAB two-component regulatory system, which controls gene expression and increases aminoglycoside resistance. The intricate structure of a biofilm can shield the bacteria from the host's immune system and antimicrobial medications [19]. The general defenses against antibiotic attack that biofilm-mediated resistance provides for bacteria include inhibiting the penetration of antibiotics, modifying the microenvironment to cause sluggish growth of biofilm cells, triggering adaptive stress responses, and maintaining cell differentiation. Drug resistance mediated by biofilms is adaptive; antibiotic susceptibility can increase quickly when bacteria are no longer protected by their biofilm. *P. aeruginosa*-caused chronic infections have been shown to be typically followed by the development of biofilms [20]. Although *P. aeruginosa*'s adaptive resistance mechanism to biofilm-mediated resistance is linked to *aeruginosa* infection and recurrence.

3. Modification of Drug Targets

3.1 Methylation of 16S rRNA Ribosomal Subunit:

Acquired 16S rRNA methyltransferase, which uses S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) as a cofactor to add methyl groups to certain residues in the 16S rDNA site, is one route of clinically meaningful drug resistance. AGAs have a lower affinity for 16S rRNA that has methyl groups added to it than for the original 16S rRNA, which results in broad-spectrum and high-level aminoglycoside resistance.

There are two types of 16S-RMTases: those that have methylation nucleotide G1405 at position N7 and those that have methylated nucleotide A1408 at position N1. Afterwards, nine N7-G1405 16S-RMTases were found: ArmA, RmtA, RmtB (including RmtB1 and RmtB2 alleles), RmtC, RmtD (containing RmtD1 and RmtD2 alleles), RmtE, RmtF, RmtG, and RmtH. The amino acid sequence similarity of these N7-G1405 16S-RMTases ranges from moderate to high [21]. ArmA, RmtB, and RmtC 16S-RMTases have a high level of resistance to 4,6-disubstituted 2-DOS AGAs, whereas N7-G1405 16S-RMTases are resistant to 4,6-disubstituted 2-DOS but not to 4,5-disubstituted 2-DOS and other AGAs. The three enzymes exhibit a high degree of three-dimensional structural similarity despite having just 30% amino acid commonality.

3.2 rRNA Sequence Mutations:

Aminoglycoside resistance is typically not produced by mutations in the bacterial target, because most bacteria have many copies of the rRNA coding gene. Mutations in each copy of the gene are necessary for this method to generate aminoglycoside resistance. AGAs use the *rrs* and *tlyA* genes to influence ribosome mutation, which results in drug resistance. The *tlyA* gene, which codes for a 2'-O-methyltransferase, and the *rrs* gene, which codes for 16S rRNA, alter nucleotides C1409 in Helix 44 of 16S rRNA and C1920 in Helix 69 of 23S rRNA, respectively. The most common *rrs* gene mutations associated with AGA resistance in clinically resistant mycobacterium tuberculosis were found to be A1401G, C1402T, and G1484T [22].

3.3 Ribosomal Mutations:

A small 30S subunit made up of 16S rRNA and 20 proteins, as well as a big 50S subunit made up of 23S rRNA, 5S rRNA, and 34 proteins, make up the bacterial ribosome. AGAs attach to a portion of the ribosome 30S subunit's 16S rRNA decoding region, which causes the protein's normal assembly to be disrupted and ultimately affects bacterial reproduction [23].

The main groove of helix 69 (H69) of the 23S rRNA of the 50S big subunit is bound by several 2-DOS AGAs, including gentamicin, neomycin B, and paromomycin. This binding alters the translation on ribosomes. Protein synthesis is impeded in AGA-resistant *P. aeruginosa* by modifications to the ribosomal helix 69 conformation and the loss of the ribosomal protein UL6, which prevents the bacteria from binding to the translation initiation factor IF2. [24].

3.4 Changes of Bacterial Metabolism:

Both cellular respiration and the carbon source are significant factors in the pathogenicity of bacteria and their susceptibility to antibiotics. *P. aeruginosa*'s carbon metabolism is primarily regulated by Crc, Hfq, and a short RNA called CrcZ. By binding to the target mRNA, the catabolite repression regulatory protein (Crc) and the RNA chaperone Hfq form a complex that directly inhibits the translation of catabolic genes [25]. Hfq is essential for the creation of biofilms and also plays a role in the development of bacterial resistance to antibiotics like gentamicin.

Glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate can be reversibly converted to dihydroxyacetone phosphate by the triphosphate isomerase TpiA. This is an important step that connects glucose metabolism to phospholipid and glycerol metabolism. It has been discovered that mutations in the TpiA gene improve respiration, oxidative phosphorylation, and carbon metabolism in bacteria. This raises the membrane potential and encourages the uptake of AGA. Studies have revealed that bacteria carrying TpiA mutations had higher levels and more stable CrcZ. CrcZ mutations can improve bacteria's resistance to AGAs by restoring the expression of type III secretion system (T3SS) genes [26].

STRATEGIES TO OVERCOME BACTERIAL RESISTANCE TO AMINOGLYCOSIDE ANTIBIOTICS:

1. Structural Optimization and Modification of Aminoglycoside Antibiotics:

A major approach to addressing the issue of AGA resistance, aside from the creation of novel antibiotics, is to structurally alter current AGAs to reactivate their antimicrobial efficacy. One of the key processes granting bacteria resistance to AGAs in the context of aminoglycoside-modified enzymes is the alteration of AMEs [27]. The plasmid contains genes that encode AMEs. AMEs are responsible for catalyzing modifications to aminoglycoside hydroxyl or amine functionalities, which prevents AGAs from binding to bacterial ribosome sites and leads to drug resistance. For example, the ribosome structure and the action of AMEs have been used to build derivatives of second-generation semi-synthetic AGAs, such as sisomicin, isepamicin, and netilmicin, which are modified from gentamicin, and dibekacin, and amikacin, which are modified from kanamycin. Research is being concentrated on third-generation AGAs, which have fewer side effects and inhibit the AMEs' site of action. A modified derivative of sisomicin, plazomicin (ACHN-490) was created as a tool to prevent resistance through widespread AMEs [28]. The overall arrangement of AGAs is defined by the existence of alcohol nuclei with an aminocyclic structure (cyclohexanes with or without hydroxyl and amino acid substitution groupings), most of which are connected to AGAs. To increase its antibacterial activity, plazomicin undergoes several structural changes that restrict the AME site of action. Plazomicin shields itself from ANT (4') and APH (3) alteration because it does not have hydroxyl groups at the 3 and 4' locations. The action site of AAC (6') can be blocked by adding an unsaturated hydroxyethyl group at position 6'-NH₃. Moreover, 4-amino-2-hydroxybutanoic acid has an N-1 substitution with plazomicin, blocking AAC (3), ANT (2), and APH (2). These AMEs are frequently found in Enterobacteriaceae that produce ESBLs and are resistant to carbapenem, and they are crucial for AGA resistance.

2. Synergistic Antibacterial Strategy of AGAs Combined with Other Drugs:

AGA's adverse effects are another factor hampering its clinical utilization, in addition to bacterial resistance. The representative toxic side effects are ototoxicity induced by AGAs, cochlear nerve injury generated by ototoxicity, and nephrotoxicity caused by proximal tubular epithelial cell injury. However, when combined with other substances, AGAs have a stronger antibacterial impact than when administered alone. The study discovered that in addition to having a synergistic antibacterial action, the combination also lowers the dosage of the AGAs, which lowers the likelihood and severity of adverse effects. The synergistic antibacterial actions of AGAs in combination with reports from the past few years are compiled here.

2.1 Combination with Compounds with Antibacterial Activities:

2.1.1 Beta-Lactam Antibiotics:

Due to the synergistic antibacterial properties of β -lactam antibiotics, combinations of AGAs, like gentamicin, can improve antibiotic resistance, broaden the scope of therapeutic treatment, and speed up bacterial clearance. β -lactam antibiotics injure the bacterial cell wall without causing death, which facilitates AGA entrance into the bacterium and increases its capacity to kill it [29]. When treating serious hospital-acquired infections caused by multidrug-resistant species, like sepsis, ventilator-associated pneumonia, and acquired pneumonia, AGAs are frequently used in conjunction with β -lactam antibiotics.

2.1.2 Macrolides:

The most widely used macrolide in clinical practice is azithromycin, which has a lengthy half-life and significant antibacterial activity. AGAs and azithromycin are commonly utilized to address *P. aeruginosa* infections, and their combination can lower the amount of each antibiotic that is needed to treat a single infection. Research has demonstrated that gentamicin can impede translation and enhance azithromycin's ability to kill planktonic and biofilm cells. Prior research has demonstrated that azithromycin in combination with gentamicin or gemfloxacin significantly improves the outcome of treating genitourinary gonorrhoea [30].

2.1.3 Polymyxins:

Polymyxins are one of the most widely used medications to treat gram-negative bacteria, particularly *P. aeruginosa*. Polymyxin-sensitive and polymyxin-resistant *P. aeruginosa* showed a synergistic antibacterial activity when combined with amikacin. Polymyxin B and amikacin were used as a combined antibacterial treatment on polymyxin-sensitive *P. aeruginosa* (FADDI-PA111) and polymyxin-resistant *P. aeruginosa* (LESB58). The necessary bacterial membrane lipid levels required for the biosynthesis of phospholipids and lipopolysaccharides (LPS) were significantly reduced after their co-administration, according to a metabonomic analysis. This finding suggests that polymyxin B combined with amikacin can significantly inhibit the intermediates in LPS synthesis [31]. The primary source of LPS precursors is the pentose phosphate pathway (PPP), and early blockage of the PPP may have an antimicrobial effect. Additionally, the study discovered that while polymyxin B and amikacin did not have the same effect on LESB58, they did interfere with the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) and glycolysis pathways in FADDI-PA111. Glycolysis and the TCA cycle, which are examples of bacterial core carbohydrate metabolism, have been major targets in recent years for antibiotic research. Amikacin and polymyxin B's inhibitory effect on the pyridine nucleotide cycle (PNC) may also be a contributing factor to their synergistic antibacterial action. D-ribose-5-phosphate, a crucial first step for purine and pyrimidine metabolism in FADDI-PA111, significantly decreased as a result of the combination treatment, suggesting nucleotide degradation. The two medications together significantly affected the metabolism of proline and arginine in FADDI-PA111, which resulted in the disruption of amino acid pathways. One novel approach to combat bacterial infection and eliminate their mode of action is thought to include the disruption of amino acid pathways, represented by arginine metabolism [32].

2.1.4 Antimicrobial Peptides:

AMPs are found in many different animals and plants and have evolved from their natural state as antibiotics. They are the body's initial line of defense against pathogen invasion. Broad-spectrum resistance, quick action, and a predisposition toward low resistance are traits of AMPs. It is anticipated that AMPs will become a more popular class of antibacterial medications due to the growing resistance to current antibiotics [33]. It was discovered that AMPs and gentamicin had a partial synergistic effect ($0.5 < FLC < 1$) and a synergistic effect (fractional lethal concentration (FLC) < 0.5) against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, respectively, in the investigation of the antibacterial synergy between gentamicin and the antimicrobial peptides PMAP-36 or PRW4 against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Gentamicin and PMAP-36 or PRW4 together have a synergistic antibacterial effect on gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). This effect is due to the AMPs' ability to weaken the bacterial outer membrane and increase membrane permeability, which facilitates gentamicin's entry into the cytoplasmic membrane. Additionally, the AMPs' direct antibacterial activity is attributed to their interactions with intercellular targets, like DNA, once they have entered the bacteria. It's still unknown exactly how AMP's work in gram-positive bacteria. PMAP-36 is more hydrophobic than PRW4, according to a molecular structure analysis of the two AMPs; its hydrophobicity may encourage membrane rupture and increase antibacterial activity.

2.1.5 Combination with natural plant extract with antibacterial activity:

Plant essential oils are a significant source of extracts for natural medicine because of their antibacterial, synergistic antibacterial, and other pharmacological properties. Gentamicin and the essential oils extracted from *Anibarosaeodora* and *Pelargonium graveolens* therefore had synergistic effects during the development of higher antibacterial activity against a variety of gram-negative bacteria and gram-positive bacteria. Gentamicin's lowest effective dose may be lowered by the combination. The combination of gentamicin and this demonstrated a notable synergistic antibacterial action, particularly in the essential oil of *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Gas chromatographic analysis was used to investigate the chemical composition of essential oils. The results indicated that terpene alcohols made up a significant portion of the essential oils derived from *Anibarosaeodora* and *Pelargonium graveolens*. The breakdown of the microbial plasma membrane causes modifications in membrane permeability and intracellular substance efflux [34], which is how monoterpenes have an antibacterial effect. Gentamicin's antibacterial action is enhanced by terpene alcohols with a high content because they bind to the 30S subunit of the bacterial ribosome and block protein synthesis.

Camellia sinensis (green tea) has been shown to possess a broad spectrum of antibacterial action. According to a study, green tea has a high catechin concentration, particularly epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG). Because EGCG in green tea can damage the bacterial cell membrane and ultimately induce bacterial rupture, Research has demonstrated that EGCG and gentamicin work synergistically to significantly reduce the growth of multidrug-resistant *E. coli* and *S. aureus* bacteria [35].

An important component of Indian traditional medicine is triphala, which is made up of the dried pericarp of the fruit of three Indian plants: *Phyllanthus emblica* Linn. or *Embllica officinalis* Gaertn. (Amalaki or the Indian gooseberry, Family: Euphorbiaceae), *Terminalia bellirica* Roxb. (Bibhitaki, Family: Combretaceae), and *Myrobalans Terminalia chebula* Retz. (Haritaki, Family: Combretaceae), and *Terminalia bellirica* Retz. (Bibhitaki, Family: Combretaceae), *Terminalia bellirica* Retz. (Haritaki, Family: Combretaceae), and *Myrobalans Terminalia chebula* Retz. (Haritaki, Family: Combretaceae), (Phyllantica). Certain antibacterial action against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria is exhibited by triphala and its individual medicinal preparations. Its antibacterial action is directly correlated with its phenolic content [36]. According to a study, certain gram-negative bacilli that are resistant to many drugs exhibit a synergistic antibacterial action when combined with triphala. Phenolic substances have the ability to break down bacterial cell membranes, which contributes to the combined antibacterial action of triphala and gentamicin. The mechanism could bear similarities to the synergistic interaction between β -lactam antibiotics and gentamicin.

Brazilian red propolis has a high concentration of phenolic chemicals, the majority of which are flavonoids, which are thought to be connected to the antibacterial properties of red propolis. Antibiotic combinations with phenolic compounds have been shown in earlier research to disrupt the bacterial cell wall or cell membrane and increase antibiotic activity [37], which facilitates the entry of antibiotics into the bacterial cell. Propolis components may primarily increase antibiotic activity through this mechanism of action. Research has shown that the combination of Brazilian red propolis and gentamicin or imipenem has a synergistic effect on *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*. It has also revealed the impact of seasonal variations in humidity on resin plants. Specimens obtained during the dry season had significantly higher levels of active components in their propolis than specimens gathered during the wet season. Accordingly, the study discovered a synergistic effect when propolis harvested during the drier time is combined with either Gentamicin or imipenem [38].

2.2 Combination with Other Compounds or Materials Without Antibacterial Activity:

2.2.1 Combination with Anti-Inflammatory Analgesics:

An important side effect of total joint replacement is periprosthetic joint infection (PJI). Gentamicin, tobramycin, and vancomycin are the most common antibacterial medications used to treat PJI locally and systemically. It has been discovered that various analgesics have some antibacterial activity against certain infections [39]. Several analgesics, including opioids, sodium channel blockers, and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs), are used to treat pain following arthroplasty. We evaluated the synergistic antibacterial effects of gentamicin (a broad-spectrum antibiotic) in combination with bupivacaine, lidocaine (a sodium channel blocker), and ketorolac (NSAID) against *S. aureus*. According to the findings, the combination of gentamicin and ketorolac exhibited a synergistic antibacterial effect since its fractional inhibitory concentration index (FICI) was less than 0.4.

Other non-antibiotic medications can be used in conjunction with drug-resistant antibiotics to counteract the antibacterial action in bacteria that are resistant to many treatments [40]. Apart from their typical effects as anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic, reports have also indicated that NSAIDs work in concert with antibiotics to enhance their antibacterial activity. A study discovered that meloxicam partially synergistically worked with gentamicin and oxytetracycline in the therapy of MRSA infections utilizing NSAIDs in addition to drug-resistant antibiotics. Furthermore, there was a partial synergistic impact of Flunixin Meglumine with Gentamicin and a synergistic effect of oxytetracycline; however, more research is needed to determine the mechanism of action [41].

2.2.2 Combination with Natural Plant Extracts Without Antibacterial Activities:

Plant essential oils have pharmacological actions that include antibacterial, synergistic antibacterial, and other activities. Although having direct antibacterial activity, the essential oil of *Mikania cordifolia* (EOMc) and limonene, its main component, can cure antibiotic resistance by controlling the effect of drugs. EOMc exhibited a synergistic antibacterial activity with gentamicin and norfloxacin against *P. aeruginosa*, but EOMc decreased the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of gentamicin against *S. aureus* [42].

The saponins can modify the local chemical environment of the cell membrane and potentially affect how bacteria absorb or respond to antibiotics, the combination of glycyrrhizic acid and gentamicin has been shown to have therapeutic potential against local bacterial infections caused by vancomycin-resistant enterococci. Plumbagin, a Chinese herbal substance, enhances the efflux of the TCA cycle and the proton-motive force to create synergistic antibacterial activity, which in turn boosts the uptake of gentamicin by carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (CRKp). To increase its effectiveness and lower its dosage, it can be used with aminoglycoside antibiotics [43].

The antibacterial activity of gentamicin and norfloxacin against Gram-negative bacteria such as *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *P. aeruginosa* can be boosted by *Croton ceanothifolius* essential oil (CcEO). The two antibiotics operating inside the bacterial cell suggested that the CcEO encourages antibiotics to enter the bacterial cytoplasm and so has a synergistic impact. The MIC of CcEO against multidrug-resistant bacteria was measured, and it was discovered that all strains had MICs larger than 1,024 µg/ml, showing that CcEO has no antibacterial action. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) was used to examine CcEO, and 25 different chemical components were found. Bicyclogermacrene (26.3%), germanene D (14.7%), and E-caryophyllene (11.7%) are the principal constituents. The hypothesis put forth by the scientists stated that while CcEO is unable to directly combat bacteria, it can work in concert with antibiotics to increase membrane permeability [44].

After being separated from croton leaves, kaempferol 7-O-β-D-(6''-O-cumaroyl)-glucopyranoside flavonoids were investigated for their antibacterial and synergistic antibacterial properties. Despite lacking direct antibacterial action against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*, kaempferol 7-O-β-D-(6''-O-cumaroyl)-glucopyranoside at 128 µg/ml demonstrated a synergistic antibacterial impact on both *S. aureus* and *E. coli* when coupled with gentamicin. Flavonoids function as inhibitors of bacterial enzymes and obstruct their manufacturing routes because their hydroxyphenyl groups have an affinity for proteins [45].

2.2.3 Combination with Nanomaterials:

Nanomaterials particularly silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), exhibit a synergistic antibacterial effect when they are combined with antibiotics [46]. Antibiotics frequently trigger bacterial cell death by producing reactive oxygen species (ROS). Research has revealed that gentamicin markedly increased AgNPs' production of ROS. ROS generation is a corollary of Tween-stabilized AgNPs' antibacterial action, as demonstrated by luminol chemiluminescence (CL). When gentamicin and Tween-stabilized AgNPs were mixed, they demonstrated synergistic antibacterial activity against staphylococcus epidermidis, a bacterium resistant to gentamicin. AgNPs and antibiotics have a synergistic antibacterial impact since they can kill bacteria through multiple mechanisms [47]. AgNPs have reportedly been shown to be able to pass through bacterial cell walls, rupture cell membranes, and ultimately kill the bacterium. We also investigated the synergistic antibacterial effect of several antibiotics and AgNPs in *E. faecalis* (Ef) infection. The results showed a strong synergistic antibacterial effect of gentamicin and chloramphenicol in combination with AgNPs [48].

Graphene is a biocompatible material and possesses antibacterial, biocarrier, biosensing, and cancer-therapy properties. Graphene oxide (GO), AgNPs, and aminoglycoside antibiotics (tobramycin) were studied for their antibacterial properties against multidrug-resistant gram-negative *E. coli*. The results showed that TOB-GO-Ag exhibited the highest antibacterial activity when compared to GO, AgNPs, and tobramycin. The study examined the mechanism by which the TOB-GO-Ag composite had a synergistic antibacterial impact by breaking down the cell wall's integrity and encouraging the entry of GO and Ag⁺ ions into cells, which ultimately led to the oxidative stress process that killed the bacteria. In the meantime, tobramycin in the created composites may also have an impact on bacterial development by preventing the synthesis of new proteins [49].

When combined with antibiotics, certain compounds containing bismuth (Bi) have been shown to exhibit synergistic antibacterial actions against bacteria. The results of the study show that Bi₂S₃ nanoparticles have no antibacterial action against *S. aureus* and MRSA, but when mixed with Gentamicin, they have a synergistic antibacterial effect on MRSA. The MIC values of Bi₂S₃ nanoparticles against these two bacteria are all >1,024 µg/ml. The interaction between Bi₂S₃ and gentamicin, the breakdown of bacterial cell membranes, the rise in gentamicin concentration in bacteria, and the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in bacteria were the primary causes of the synergistic antibacterial mechanism [50].

The crystal grain size of CaCO₃ nanoparticles (CCNPs) is around 62.5 nm, and they have a comparatively uniform chain structure. Studies have found that CCNPs have the ability to transport gentamicin and increase its release period, allowing for a 24-hour total release time. Gentamicin's antibacterial efficacy can be markedly enhanced by CCNPs. Zeta potential research and microscopic observations demonstrated that CCNPs adsorbed on the surface of bacteria increased the degree of damage to the cell wall and increased the permeability of the cell membrane, which increased the rate of bacterial mortality [51].

2.2.4 Combination With Photosensitizers:

Studies have shown that the antibacterial properties of certain antibiotics when used in conjunction with photosensitizer-mediated photodynamic antimicrobial chemotherapy (PACT) are increased. Under certain wavelength light stimulation, PACT mediated by photosensitizers will produce ROS, which causes phototoxic damage to bacteria [52]. PACT has the ability to eradicate germs not only due to its antibiotic resistance pattern but also when they are in a biofilm form [53].

A xanthine dye called Rose Bengal (RB) is utilized as a photosensitizer in PACT. The research discovered that when RBPACT and gentamicin are used in biofilm at their maximum tested concentrations of 64 µg/ml and 40 µg/ml, respectively, a synergistic antibacterial effect is observed on planktonic *S. aureus*. The mechanism by which it has a synergistic antibacterial effect is that, following bacterial cell damage, PACT stimulates the entry of gentamicin into bacteria. The bacterial ribosome's 30S subunit is subsequently bound by gentamicin, which inhibits protein synthesis and eventually causes bacterial death [54].

Toluidine blue (TB), a hydrophilic cationic alkaline photosensitizer (PS), is a photobacterial agent. It is thought that tuberculosis (TB) damages bacterial membranes because of its strong affinity for them [55]. Subsequent research revealed that TB-PACT plus gentamicin exhibited a significantly greater synergistic antibacterial action against *S. aureus* and MRSA than did either medication by itself. Antimicrobial photodynamic treatment (aPDT) uses light irradiation to break the outer membrane of bacterial cells, which is thought to facilitate the passage of antibacterial medications. Gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria are both impacted by the growth of LED light-emitting diodes (LEDs) when exposed to blue light. Blue LED light demonstrated a synergistic antibacterial effect on *E. coli* and *S. aureus* when combined with AGAs like amikacin and gentamicin. It also promoted the inactivation of the bacteria, which may be related to the antibacterial effect caused by oxidative stress [56].

CONCLUSION

AGAs have a broad antibacterial range, high antibacterial activity, and good water solubility, which makes them popular in clinical applications. Their broad range of applications has limited their clinical utilization due to adverse effect manifestation and rising bacterial resistance. Reversing bacterial resistance to AGAs has been possible in recent years thanks to ongoing research on the compound that has deepened our understanding of both the resistance mechanism and the antibacterial mode of action. The strategies involve providing the new charm of existing AGAs and structurally modifying older AGAs based on new target prediction of existing AGAs in an effort to recover their antibacterial activity. AGAs exhibit good antibacterial efficacy with fewer side effects when coupled with other antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic medications, natural plant extracts, and other compounds. This synergistic antibacterial effect allows for a reduction in the dosage of individual medications. AGAs are projected to have a promising future since medication combinations are likely to improve the increasingly severe bacterial drug resistance, as many pharmaceuticals with theoretical foundations have synergistic antibacterial activity in the experimental stage. Combining antibiotics with additional medications is a crucial tactic for combating bacterial resistance.

Anticipating the traditional AGAs pharmacological targets and delving into the key mechanisms of bacterial growth could pave the way for the discovery of novel AGAs derivatives and compounds that combine AGAs.

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